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ATHENS Course on Application of Ionizing Radiation

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ABSTRACT

The **ATHENS Programme** (Advanced Technology Higher Education Network/Socrates) is a 1-week exchange session, held twice a year (usually in March and November), by a network of 15 leading European technological universities. The Czech Technical University takes part in this programme since 2003. The case study of one of the courses, the Course on Application of Ionizing Radiation, is a subject of this paper. The course consists of 14 hours of lectures, 8 hours of experimental exercises and 3 hours of experimental demonstrations. The excursion into the Proton Therapy Centre and to the National Technical Museum is also included. This programme covers representative applications of ionizing radiation in various branches of human activities. In general, using radiation for diagnostics and therapy in medicine is more or less known to general public, however the course covers also the less known and discussed fields, as e.g. applications in geology and geophysics, art and archaeometry, and for analytical purposes. Some information about radiation protection and environmental radioactivity is also included. 20 students took part in this course in the March 2017 Session, from 8 universities. Except description of the course, the paper summarises also some feedback from students, which serves as the background for improving future runs of the course.

Conference Key Areas: Physics and Engineering Education, Skills and Engineering Education, Curriculum Development

Keywords: ATHENS course, application of ionizing radiation, course programme, feedback.

INTRODUCTION

The **ATHENS Programme** (Advanced Technology Higher Education Network/Socrates Programme) consists of 1-week exchange sessions, held twice a year (usually in March and November), organised by a network of 15 leading European universities of technology. The programme is aimed at carrying out intensive specialization courses, given at each member institution, enabling students to attend one of the courses offered by the network universities during 7 days. Since the groups of students are international, the language of the courses is English. The objective is to give students a brief immersion in another European education system. Each institution defines the number of credits given to its students participating in ATHENS courses (generally 2 or 3 ECTS credits, but some universities including CTU give no credits). Students are asked to evaluate the course they attended by filling an on-line evaluation form at the end of each Session. This experience, in many cases, gives students the desire to carry out studies of a longer duration (MSc and PhD levels) at an institution different from their home institution and thus facilitates exchanges between students of the major European technological institutions. About 60 courses are offered in each ATHENS Session.

The programme is coordinated by the ParisTech. It was established with the support of the European Communities SOCRATES Programme with annual subsidy from 1997-2001. Today, the Programme is mainly founded by contributions from the member universities. This is a disadvantage, as universities have usually limited and insufficient budgets all over the Europe and they do not cover full expenses to students (e.g., CTU covers about 60 % of living expenses and full travel expenses, if they do not exceed some limits given by varying distances to the destinations). The courses cover the wide spectrum of fields, mostly in science and technology, but they are also opened to arts and humanities [1].

Usefulness of this programme is out of any doubts. Science and technology are not the most popular disciplines among young people and any international programme at the good level can contribute to the attractiveness of studies at technical universities. And, moreover, such short time stays do not interfere substantially with study plans at the mother university, but they can bring an intensive view into a different country, a different university, a different branch of study and a different study system.

The Czech Technical University takes part in this programme since 2003. Its faculties offered the following courses for the ATHENS March 2017 Session [2]:

- Application of Ionising Radiation
- Text Searching Algorithms
- The PIV Method in Fluid Mechanics
- Management and Economics
- Introduction to Vibrational Spectroscopy
- Talent Management

The case study of one of these courses, the Course on Application of Ionising Radiation, is a subject of this paper.

1 OBJECTIVES AND STRUCTURE OF THE COURSE

The course is carried out by the Department of Dosimetry and Application of Ionising Radiation of the Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering of the Czech Technical University in Prague. This faculty was established in 1955 in connection with

starting the Czechoslovak nuclear programme, and though it added also some non-nuclear topics into its profile (mostly applied mathematics and non-nuclear parts of physics) during the years of its existence, it is still one of the strongest educational institutions in nuclear branches of science and technology in Europe. It covers practically the whole spectrum of nuclear and radiation theory, experimental practice and applications, having even its own small school nuclear reactor and its own small tokamak, both mostly for educational purposes.

The objective of the course is to obtain an overview of the theoretical and experimental background, concerning the application of ionizing radiation and radionuclides in industry and medicine. Depending on the mode of application, information is in most cases obtained through effects of radiation on matter. Detection and evaluation of radiation can give the desired information about these effects. The state of applications is described in lectures, but it is also implemented in the laboratory classes and experimental demonstrations.

The programme consists of:

A) Seven 2-hour lectures:

- Characteristic of Ionizing Radiation and Radioactivity
- X Ray Fluorescence Analysis
- Application of Ionizing Radiation in Geology and Geophysics
- Application of Radiation in Art and Archaeometry
- Radon-Problem in Radiation Protection
- Application of Ionizing Radiation in Medicine
- Personal Dosimetry and Radiation Protection

B) Four 2-hour experimental exercises:

- Polymer-gel dosimetry
- Spectrometry of Gamma Radiation with HP(Ge) Detector
- X Ray Fluorescence Analysis
- Personal Dosimetry - TLD

C) Two 2-hour experimental demonstrations:

- GOLEM - Tokamak thermonuclear installation
- Application of Ionizing Radiation in Medicine

As seen, this programme covers representative applications of ionizing radiation in various branches of human activities. Generally, using radiation for diagnostics and therapy in medicine is more or less known (though usually not from the point of view of physical principles) in general public, however the course covers also the less known fields, as e.g. applications in geology and geophysics, art and archaeometry, and for analytical purposes. Moreover, also scientific books about applications of ionising radiation (except applications in medicine and health physics) are not too frequently published. It is evident that it is not possible to cover all the issues connected with extensive use of ionizing radiation within a week, but the programme of the course can arouse students' interest in it, including links to the further educational literature for serious candidates. Let us bring at least two references for those, who want to make themselves more familiar with these issues, or for those, who want to follow us in our effort to extend knowledge of students in this field. [3, 4].

Some social activities are also included, mostly with the aim to make participants familiar with the city and the students' life. First of all, this is the orientation meeting during the first day of their stay, which gives to participants the basic information about

the city and the university, and then some so-called European dimension activities: the Prague guided walk, the Prague discovery game, which is an unusual sightseeing in a form of a special game for groups, which ends by a dinner at a secret place, the Country presentations in the popular youth club, and finally, the Farewell dinner in the students' restaurant. Some of these activities are organised by our students from the CTU Student Union and from the CTU International Student Club.

As a part of the social programme, the excursion into the National Technical Museum was also included. NTM is one of the most popular and important museums in Prague and, after recent complete restoration and renovation of both the building and the collections, it is also one of the best technical museums in Europe. It is to some extent oriented not only to technology, but also to science [5].

The programme is intended for advanced students, who should be familiar with general mathematics and physics at the level of standard courses at technical universities. Moreover, some knowledge of atomic and nuclear physics and of interaction of ionising radiation with matter is necessary.

Students receive copies of ppt presentations of all lectures and manuals for the practical exercises in advance. The course is finished by a written exam of 2 hours duration, which, however, is relatively simple and failure is very rare.

2 THE POINT OF VIEW OF LECTURERS

20 students (which is the maximum capacity due to the capacity of laboratories for practical exercises) took part in the course in the March 2017 Session, from 8 universities (9 students from the KU Leuven, 3 from the TU Wien, 2 from the École Supérieure de Physique et de Chimie Industrielles de la Ville de Paris, 1 from the Mines ParisTech, 1 from the Warsaw University of Technology, 2 from the Politecnico di Milano, 1 from the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and 1 from the Technische Universität München). The main problem of these courses (not only of this one, but also of the other courses in the past and on the other topics) was that the participants were put together mostly by their interest on the topic. Though they all were from the top technical universities, they were as a minimum in the 4th year of study, and some knowledge of radiation physics was a necessary prerequisite, they had different background in physics and mathematics. This means that both lectures and exercises needed to be built on rather general explanatory level, to be understandable for all participants. On the other hand, we had not noticed any language problems, the level of English of all participating students was very good.

March or November dates of the courses, which are prescribed by the ATHENS Programme, are not too suitably chosen from the point of view of usual weather conditions. Participants may arrive on Friday and have a free weekend, which they can use for sightseeing. Prague is a very nice and interesting city, but these months are not the best ones for this purpose (on the other hand, this period is out of the main touristic season and Prague is not so overcrowded by tourists). However, the more important problem is that these dates coincide with teaching in the summer or in the winter semester, and therefore it is a bit difficult to harmonize the course schedule with the schedule of standard courses for our students. This difficulty not so much concerns the lectures, which is easier to organise, but finding space for laboratory exercises, which substantially contribute to the attractiveness of the course, is not easy.

And last but not least, organising and teaching in these courses asks for some enthusiasm of both teachers and students. As mentioned above, the ATHENS

Programme started with the support of the European Communities, which helped to prepare the structure of the courses and was a perfect starting motion. However, it is nowadays financed by participating universities and participants, which means that it operates with the limited budget, cheap accommodation for participants has comfort corresponding to the low costs, etc.

3 THE POINT OF VIEW OF STUDENTS

The feedback from students was obtained by discussion with them, and by a questionnaire they complete. They marked each lecture and exercise in the scale from 1 (the best) to 4 (the worst), which followed the old system of classification of exams before introducing the Bologna system and was fully satisfactory for this purpose. The mean value of such classification was mostly between 1.5 and 2, usually with slightly better values for exercises than for lectures. Surprisingly, the excursion into the Prague Proton Therapy Centre, the very modern medical installation, using the most advanced radiation therapy methods, which was included this year as the practical demonstration of application of ionising radiation in medicine, obtained relatively low rating (2,36). Possible explanation is the little pedagogical experience of a Center employee who accompanied the students and gave them an interpretation. General organisation and the level of course materials were also evaluated, the ratings were very positive this year (no mark 3 or 4, the mean values 1,24 and 1,28).

Students may also use this opportunity for verbal expression of their opinion. Unfortunately, this is sometimes readable only with difficulties, and sometimes the opinion of various students is self-contradictory, nevertheless it gives some more complex picture and feedback. Let us give some responses to individual lectures (without any order of importance and without any language corrections):

- A little too much material on some slides; some introductory theory (on slides, not orally) would be useful.
- Great material, maybe spend more time on this material.
- A little monotonous.
- Nice effort of interactivity.
- Too many examples of application.
- Out of interest field.
- Very clean and illustrative lecture.
- Out of interest but good lecture anyhow.
- It is sad that it comes on Friday morning.
- I am not interested in art, but I understand it is an important topic.
- Too much theory, more examples would be better.
- Too much applications and examples.
- Sometimes too much details.
- Interesting because of examples he brought.
- A lot of repetitive examples.
- Maybe he has to speak more quickly and increase the program.
- The first part (Technical) was good, but the examples were too many.
- Not enough detail, would be good to have more insight about diagnostic techniques.
- It was nice to have all the examples.

And some responses to practical exercises:

- Not much theory, chemistry explanations would be useful.
- A bit short in time.
- Theory is not well explained and much more complicated than we were told.
- Interesting technique, good assistant.
- The assistant did not look very enthusiastic.
- It was a pleasure to go to those practical exercises.
- Interesting, but not so many to do.
- We were not allowed to do much, not so interesting.
- I appreciate the professor. It was very funny.

About the visit in the Proton Therapy Centre:

- Lack of motivation and I did not understand at all the explanation, what is bad, because it would be very interesting.
- Nice centre and technology, but the guide was not skilled enough to attract the full audience.
- The guide could not explain it very well, otherwise it might be interesting.
- It was experience for my whole life. I was really interested!!!
- It was interesting to see the concrete implementation, but I would like to have more links with the theoretical aspects.
- Bad general explanations for the entire group from the guide.
- Interesting, but the guide was not passionate about presenting it.
- Maybe it is better to do a lecture before the visit.

As seen from these more or less randomly selected responses (however legibility of the hand-written comments played also some role in this selection), this survey, in which all participants of the course took place, gave the wide, though sometimes a bit contradictory view to the course. Some repeating comments to individual parts of the course should be used in preparing the next run. For example, some lectures were criticised for too many slides, too much text on slides or for too many similar examples of applications. There is no problem to reduce it. Revising and extending theoretical explanations of practical exercises would also be useful. Good relations of our department with the Proton Therapy Centre allow us to ask next time for some other expert from the staff for guiding and explanations. The problem, which, however, cannot be easily solved, is connected with differing interests of participants. They know the topics of the course in advance from the complete programme on the web pages of the ATHENS Programme, and if they claim in their responses, that they are not interested in chemistry, art or anything else, they must be reconciled with the fact, that these issues are mentioned. But it is possible to say, that in general the theoretical and practical parts of lectures, exercises and the course as a whole are well balanced.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The ATHENS Programme is a good example of activities, which liven up the “standard” university courses and extend the spectrum of topics taught in them with minimum time load for students. Nevertheless, they lose one week during the running semester at their university. One week stay at the university abroad is quite short time for making acquaintance with the university, the city and the country. However, it can awaken deeper interest in the university or in the topics of the course. Good quality is the necessary prerequisite of universities participating in this programme, and therefore, good quality of courses, lectures and students can also be expected.

The course on application of ionising radiation has been step by step improved according the responses of participants during the past years. Some improvements are still possible, as nobody and nothing is perfect, but we see that majority of students express their satisfaction with its quality. Moreover, the topics of the course are included into study programmes only at a few European universities. The Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering of the Czech Technical University can take advantage from its more than 60 years long tradition in the field of nuclear sciences.

The ATHENS Programme is probably less known than some other programmes of student exchanges, especially as the ERASMUS Programme, and it is also less universal, being limited only to 15 participating technical universities. Its contribution to the European dimensions of engineering education is, however, non-negligible. And, said with some exaggeration, we are prepared to polish our course to full perfection.

The next ATHENS session will be held on 11-18 November 2017.

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